

Organizational Commitment as Intervening Variables on the Effect of Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice and Interactional Justice on Job Satisfaction (Case Study: Sales & Distribution Division of Food FMCG Company in Indonesia)

Hafizh Nazhar Pahlevi¹, Farida Elmi²

Faculty of Economics and Business, Mercu Buana University Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:-

Objectives: This study aims to determine the effect of distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice through organizational commitment as an intervening variable on job satisfaction in the sales & distribution division of food FMCG company in Indonesia.

Methodology/approach: This study uses the SEM PLS analysis method where the data processing uses the SmartPLS 3.2.9 application. Based on the results of research by distributing questionnaires to 136 employees.

Finding: From this study, it was found that there is a positive and significant effect of distributive justice on job satisfaction, procedural justice on job satisfaction, procedural justice on organizational commitment, interactional justice on organizational commitment, organizational commitment on job satisfaction.

Novelty/Value: This research has contributed to the development of existing research construct models. The contribution of distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice variables to job satisfaction. The contribution of distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice variables to organizational commitment. The contribution of organizational commitment variable to job satisfaction.

Keywords:- Organizational Commitment, Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice, Interactional Justice and Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are an important factor that must exist in the organization as the achievement of goals and system administrators. In order for the system to work, of course, its management must pay attention to several important aspects, such as distributive justice, procedural justice, supervision, and interactive justice. If all aspects of justice are met, then job satisfaction will be achieved. Injustice in an organization is a dysfunctional practice of the organization which has an impact on the uncomfortable working atmosphere in the organization. People in the organization are very concerned with making fair decisions,

they believe that if the organization carries out its procedures fairly, both the organization and its employees will get benefit. Organizational commitment as the most popular concept of a one-dimensional structure or better known as the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ). OCQ proposed by Allen and Meyer (1990)

Organizational commitment as a multi-dimensional structure consists of three components, affective, continuous and normative (Meyer et al., 1993). Report from the NielsenIQ Consumer Survey Institute (2021) in its survey shows that the contribution of Indonesian consumer spending on food spending still reached 22% in the first quarter of 2021. Although it decreased by 1% compared to last year in the same period, compared to consumer spending in other categories, the figure was still the largest. The Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) food industry is the same as other fields, the Sales & Distribution Division will be the spearhead in achieving turnover (income) from the business and become an element that will intersect directly with external parties. Therefore, each element of the Sales & Distribution Division must have a good & correct process from upstream to downstream in terms of resources.

The results of the pre-survey of Procedural Justice, it can be seen that the Procedural Fairness of employees is still quite low, especially on the dimensions of Bias Suppression and ethics. While the results of the pre-survey of Interactional Justice, and it can be seen that the Interactional Justice of employees is still quite low, especially on the dimension of Interpersonal Justice. Furthermore, the results of the pre-survey of Distributive Justice, and it can be seen that the Distributive Justice of employees is still quite low, especially in the dimensions of Equality & Qualification. And the results of the pre-survey of Organizational Commitment, it can be seen that the Organizational Commitment of employees is still quite low, especially on the dimension of Affective Commitment. Research conducted by Sunaryo (2020) at PT. A states that distributive justice and procedural justice have no effect on job satisfaction. Research conducted by Annisa & Mayliza (2019) at Nagari Bank resulted that interactional justice had no effect on employee job satisfaction. The same results were also obtained in research conducted by Indahyati & Sintasih (2019) that procedural justice and interactional justice did not significantly affect job satisfaction. In accordance with research conducted by Bakhsi & Kumar in

Indahyati & Sintasih (2019) that there is no relationship between procedural justice and job satisfaction.

The results of research conducted by Lotfi & Pour in Indahyati & Sintaasih (2019) consistently state that interactional justice has no effect on job satisfaction. From previous research, there are still research gaps. So it is necessary to know and analyze more about Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable on the Effect of Distributive Justice, Procedural Fairness, and Interactional Justice on Job Satisfaction, this is the purpose of this research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Distributive Justice*

According to Colquitt (2012), distributive justice refers to the balance of distribution of organizational results in the form of wages, benefits, and bonuses. When individuals in the organization feel that the proportion of investment rewards they receive is balanced, they feel fair, which indicates the existence of distributive justice. Distributive justice is conceptualized as justice related to decision-making outcomes and resource allocation. Outcomes or resources can be tangible (such as compensation) or intangible (such as praise). Perceptions of distributive justice can be balanced with inputs. Yamagishi believes (cited by Faturochman, 2002) that distributive justice in psychology includes all forms of distribution between group members and communication between two people. Expected distributional justice is not only related to giving, but also includes distribution, placement, and exchange. The indicators for measuring Distributive Justice use measurement items developed by Colquitt (2012), that is: Equality shows an assessment of equality between the efforts made at work and the rewards received. Qualification indicates an assessment of the eligibility of benefits provided by the company based on the completion of the work. Contribution shows the evaluation of the application of awards and contributions to the company. Performance shows an assessment of the validity of the resulting performance with the rewards received.

B. *Procedural Justice*

Procedural justice is concerned with evaluating fairness through policies and procedures adopted in decision making (Greenberg, 1990; Hounstein et al., 2001). Procedural fairness is an individual's perception of the fairness of the process used to determine various outcomes. The procedural justice model aims to explain that procedural justice gives groups a view of their own interests (Haerani et al., 2020; Brown et al., 2005). In this model, the group means that the justice felt by employees is that they need each other and work together in carrying out their duties. According to (Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2006) a company has established procedures. Colquitt (2012) shows that there are six indicators of procedural justice. If each of these rules can be met, then the procedure can be said to be fair. The following are related rules, that is : Consistency Rule, The Bias Suppression Rule, The Accuracy Rule, The

Correctability Rule, The Representativeness Rule, The Ethicality Rule..

C. *Interactional Justice*

Interactional justice is the key to forming work motivation and commitment to the organization. Interactional justice is justice that describes how leaders treat people who are bound by their authority, decisions, and actions (Crueru and Macerscu, 2009). Interactional justice involves perceptions of fairness communication that is involved in organizational justice (Hubbel and Chory-Assad, 2005). 6). According to (Cropanzano et al., 2007) there are at least two indicators of Interactional justice, those are: Interpersonal Justice by treating employees with dignity, courtesy, respect and respect and Informational Justice by sharing relevant information between superiors and employees or between employees and coworkers.

D. *Organizational Commitment*

The dimensions of organizational commitment used in this study are the dimensions of Meyer and Allen in Widodo (2010) which explain that there are three separate dimensions of organizational commitment, those are: Affective Commitment Emotional attachment, identification and involvement of an employee in an organization. Employees who have a strong affective commitment stay with the organization because they want to work for the organization. Continuance Commitment is an employee's commitment based on consideration of what must be sacrificed when leaving the organization or the loss that will be obtained by the employee if he does not continue his work in the organization.

Employees who have high continuance commitment will be in the organization because they really need to work for the organization. Normative commitment is the commitment of employees to their organization because of their obligation to stay in the organization for moral or ethical reasons, or in other words, employees' beliefs regarding their responsibilities to the organization. This is the right thing to do. This commitment relates to employees' feelings about the need to stay in the organization. Therefore, employees who have high normative commitment will stay in the organization because they feel obliged or should be loyal to the organization. Measurement of employee commitment uses four indicators developed by Mowday et al (in Rimata 2014: 5), those are : Strong desire to remain as a member Willingness to work hard and Acceptance of organizational values.

E. *Job Satisfaction*

McShane and Glinow (2008) explain that job satisfaction is an individual's evaluation of work and work environment. Luthans (2008) describes job satisfaction as an employee's perception of the completion of tasks that they consider as important. Luthans points out that there are three generally accepted dimensions of job satisfaction, those are : Job satisfaction is an emotional response to a work situation. Therefore, it cannot be seen, it can only be concluded. Job satisfaction usually depends on how well results meet or exceed expectations. For example, if organizational

participants feel that they work harder than others in the department, but get less reward, they may have negative attitudes toward their boss, work, and/or coworkers, and they will feel dissatisfied. On the other hand, if they feel they have been treated well and paid fairly, they are more likely to have a positive attitude towards the job and be satisfied with the job.

III. METHODS

The research design used is a causal research design which aims to test the hypothesis about the effect of one or several variables (independent variables) on the dependent variable (Sekaran, 2017). Construct measurement is the development of the theories used. Colquitt (2012), (Gilliand & Chan, 2001) Cropanzano et al (2007) (Robbins and Judge, 2008). Greenberg, 1990: Hounstein et al., 2001). Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2006) (Cruceu and Macerscu, 2009) Vizano et al., (2018) Meyer and Allen in Widodo (2010) Mowday et al (in Rimata 2014:5) (Mangkunegara, 2016).

According to Sugiyono, (2017) the research sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population so that the sample taken from the population must be truly representative. The sampling technique used in this study is non-probability sampling, which is a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. The type of non-probability sampling used in this study is census sampling (saturated), which is a sampling technique when all members of the population are sampled. Thus the sample used in this study was 136 employees.

In this study, the data collection technique used was a survey method by distributing questionnaires to employees. In this questionnaire data, the researcher used a Likert Scale in the answer choices. According to Sugiyono (2017), the Likert Scale itself is a method used to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. The variables in this study will be measured and translated into indicator variables and the answers to each instrument item will have a gradation from very positive to very negative.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the description of the respondents described the characteristics of the respondents consisting of gender, age and education. Below is an explanation of the description of the respondents.

Characteristics of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	84	61,8 %
Female	52	38,2 %
Age		
<20 years old	15	11 %
20 – 30years old	49	36 %
31 -40years old	46	34 %
41 -50years old	26	19 %
Last education		
High School	35	26%
Bachelor Degree (S-1)	101	74 %
TOTAL	136	100 %

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

The data is processed using SEM-PLS through the SmartPLS 3.2.9 application with the analysis stages, namely Outer Model Evaluation & Inner Model Evaluation. The data

is processed using SEM-PLS through the SmartPLS 3.2.9 application with the analysis stages, namely Outer Model Evaluation & Inner Model Evaluation.

Fig. 1: Loading Factor Results

The standard value of loading factor > 0.70 (Ghozali, 2015). The results of the loading factor and AVE as shown in the following table.

Latent Variable	Manifest Variable (Indicator)	Loading Factor	Information
Distributive Justice	X1.1	0,794	Valid
	X1.3	0,783	Valid
	X1.5	0,771	Valid
	X1.7	0,892	Valid
	X1.9	0,782	Valid
	X1.10	0,761	Valid
	X1.11	0,883	Valid
Procedural Justice	X2.1	0,800	Valid
	X2.2	0,788	Valid
	X2.3	0,726	Valid
	X2.5	0,887	Valid
	X2.7	0,818	Valid
	X2.9	0,839	Valid
	X2.10	0,788	Valid
	X2.11	0,828	Valid
	X2.13	0,856	Valid
	X2.14	0,825	Valid
	X2.15	0,795	Valid
Interactional Justice	X3.1	0,857	Valid
	X3.2	0,906	Valid
	X3.3	0,864	Valid
	X3.4	0,892	Valid
	X3.5	0,790	Valid
	X3.6	0,831	Valid
Job Satisfaction	Y.1	0,740	Valid
	Y.2	0,785	Valid
	Y.3	0,836	Valid
	Y.4	0,872	Valid
	Y.6	0,827	Valid
	Y.9	0,826	Valid
	Y.10	0,819	Valid
Organizational Commitment	Z.2	0,857	Valid
	Z.5	0,828	Valid
	Z.7	0,753	Valid
	Z.9	0,879	Valid
	Z.12	0,815	Valid
	Z.13	0,865	Valid

Table 2: Loading Factor Value of All Constructs

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Distributive Justice	0,658
Procedural Justice	0,673
Interactional Justice	0,735
Organizational Commitment	0,695
Job Satisfaction	0,666

Table 3: Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of All Constructs

Based on the results of the re-estimation of the loading factor, the item values generated by the constructs of Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice, Interactional Justice, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment have met the standard value of convergent validity because the factor

is worth more than 0.7. Thus, it can be concluded that all constructs are valid. In addition, convergent validity can also be seen from the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value with good value criteria above 0.5 (Ghozali, 2015).

	Distributive Justice	Procedural Justice	Interactional Justice	Organizational Commitment	Job Satisfaction
X1.1	0,794	0,716	0,742	0,710	0,698
X1.3	0,783	0,712	0,632	0,697	0,694
X1.5	0,771	0,664	0,770	0,689	0,688
X1.7	0,892	0,876	0,872	0,834	0,830
X1.9	0,782	0,693	0,620	0,627	0,697
X1.10	0,761	0,652	0,621	0,612	0,629
X1.11	0,883	0,786	0,820	0,751	0,795
X2.1	0,743	0,800	0,747	0,766	0,795
X2.2	0,638	0,788	0,645	0,689	0,734
X2.3	0,657	0,726	0,664	0,616	0,675
X2.5	0,786	0,887	0,778	0,800	0,825
X2.7	0,663	0,818	0,676	0,664	0,779
X2.9	0,763	0,839	0,731	0,708	0,821
X2.10	0,754	0,788	0,709	0,678	0,746
X2.11	0,728	0,828	0,802	0,717	0,800
X2.13	0,791	0,856	0,704	0,774	0,785
X2.14	0,762	0,825	0,730	0,705	0,780
X2.15	0,680	0,795	0,708	0,683	0,783
X2.16	0,629	0,751	0,607	0,718	0,699
X2.17	0,809	0,853	0,776	0,834	0,812
X2.18	0,838	0,913	0,800	0,787	0,853
X3.1	0,781	0,718	0,857	0,680	0,741
X3.2	0,844	0,788	0,906	0,754	0,784
X3.3	0,760	0,761	0,864	0,712	0,770
X3.4	0,814	0,826	0,892	0,807	0,792
X3.5	0,663	0,784	0,790	0,712	0,782
X3.6	0,768	0,679	0,831	0,697	0,681
Z.2	0,757	0,763	0,715	0,857	0,744
Z.5	0,643	0,696	0,697	0,828	0,686
Z.7	0,636	0,632	0,579	0,753	0,634
Z.9	0,796	0,818	0,806	0,879	0,872
Z.12	0,716	0,746	0,700	0,815	0,719
Z.13	0,791	0,756	0,732	0,865	0,721
Y.1	0,729	0,690	0,703	0,695	0,740
Y.2	0,648	0,721	0,641	0,650	0,785
Y.3	0,713	0,768	0,732	0,673	0,836
Y.4	0,746	0,832	0,753	0,714	0,872
Y.6	0,717	0,816	0,697	0,726	0,827
Y.9	0,807	0,819	0,803	0,785	0,826
Y.10	0,703	0,775	0,772	0,780	0,819
Y.12	0,713	0,775	0,676	0,714	0,817

Table 4: Loading Factor of All Constructs

The loading factor value for each indicator shown in the table above (blocked and bold values) is greater than the

cross loading value. So, this shows that all indicators in this research are valid.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Distributive Justice	0,912	0,931
Procedural Justice	0,962	0,966
Interactional Justice	0,927	0,943
Organizational Commitment	0,912	0,932
Job Satisfaction	0,928	0,941

Table 5: The results of the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

The results of the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha measurements shown in the table above state that the reliability of this study meets the standards and has a high value. The inner model examines the relationship between constructs or latent variables by

looking at the estimated parameter coefficients and significance. Measurements included R2 and t-tests to examine hypothetical relationships.

R-Square is used to measure the predictive power of a structural model. R-Squares explains the effect of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables whether they have a substantive effect. R-

squares values of 0.67, 0.33 and 0.19 indicate strong, moderate and weak models (Chin, 1998 in Ghozali and Latan, 2015).

	R Square	R Square Adjusted	Information
Organizational Commitment	0,816	0,811	Strong
Job Satisfaction	0,917	0,914	Strong

Table 6: R-Square Value

The F-Square test is carried out to see the effect of exogenous latent variables on endogenous variables whether they have a substantive effect. The recommended interpretation of the F-Square value is >

0.02, which has a weak effect; > 0.15 has a moderate effect and > 0.35 has a strong effect. The results are as follows.

	Organizational Commitment	Job Satisfaction
Distributive Justice	0,069	0,024
Procedural Justice	0,185	0,723
Interactional Justice	0,022	0,036
Organizational Commitment		0,831

Table 7: F-Square Value

The Q-Square test was conducted to determine the predictive relevance of the compiled model, the test was carried out from a blindfolding process. From the test results it was found that the Q-Square values of the

compiled models were all > 0, so that the model was declared to have met predictive relevance where the model had been properly reconstructed. The results are shown in the following table.

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Distributive Justice	952,000	952,000	
Procedural Justice	1904,000	1904,000	
Interactional Justice	816,000	816,000	
Organizational Commitment	816,000	361,336	0,557
Job Satisfaction	1088,000	431,491	0,603

Table 8: Q-Square Value

To find out whether a hypothesis is accepted or rejected can be done by paying attention to the significance value between constructs, t-statistics and p-values. In this way, the measurement estimates and standard errors are no longer calculated with statistical assumptions, but are based on empirical observations. In the bootstrap resampling method in this study, the hypothesis is accepted if the significance value of the t-values is greater than 1.658 and

or the p-values are less than 0.05, then Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected and vice versa. Significance values can be calculated using the bootstrapping method, which is a process for assessing the level of significance or probability of direct effects and indirect effects. For the direct effect, it can be seen directly from the path coefficient and to see the indirect effect of the constructs described in the model, it can be seen from the specific indirect effect.

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Direct Effect					
X1 -> Y	0,159	0,157	0,088	1,821	0,035
X2 -> Y	0,680	0,686	0,069	9,886	0,000
X3 -> Y	0,139	0,132	0,075	1,864	0,031
Z -> Y	0,191	0,117	0,066	2,897	0,002
X1 -> Z	0,303	0,303	0,118	2,581	0,005
X2 -> Z	0,470	0,474	0,112	4,196	0,000
X3 -> Z	0,220	0,157	0,058	3,821	0,000
Indirect Effect					
X1 -> Z -> Y	0,028	0,035	0,014	1,994	0,024
X2 -> Z -> Y	0,078	0,055	0,032	2,431	0,008
X3 -> Z -> Y	0,020	0,020	0,009	2,360	0,010

Table 9: Path Coefficient (Direct Effect) & Specific Indirect Effect

Fig. 2: Bootstrapping Result

Hypothesis	Path	t-value	t-table	Decision
Hypothesis 1	X1 -> Y	1,821	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 2	X2 -> Y	9,886	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 3	X3 -> Y	1,864	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 4	Z -> Y	2,897	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 5	X1 -> Z	2,581	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 6	X2 -> Z	4,196	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 7	X3 -> Z	3,821	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 8	X1 -> Z -> Y	1,994	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 9	X2 -> Z -> Y	2,431	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted
Hypothesis 10	X3 -> Z -> Y	2,360	1,658	Hypothesis Accepted

Table 10: Hypothesis Test Results

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H1 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Distributive Justice of Food FMCG employees affects the level of Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H2 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Procedural Justice of Food FMCG employees affects the level of Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H3 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Interactional Justice of Food FMCG employees affects the level of Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H4 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Organizational Commitment that exists in Food FMCG employees can affect the level of Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H5 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Distributive Justice of Food FMCG employees affects the level of Organizational Commitment of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H6 was accepted. The results of this test state that Procedural Justice in Food FMCG employees can affect the level of Organizational Commitment held by Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H7 was accepted. The results of this test state that Interactional Justice in Food FMCG employees can affect the level of Organizational Commitment held by Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H8 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Organizational Commitment of Food FMCG employees can support the effect of Distributive Justice in Food FMCG employees on Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H9 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Organizational Commitment of Food FMCG employees can support the influence of Procedural Justice of Food FMCG employees on Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that H10 was accepted. The results of this test state that the Organizational Commitment of Food FMCG employees can support the influence of Interactional Justice of Food FMCG employees on Job Satisfaction of Food FMCG employees.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion on Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable on the Effect of Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice, and Interactional Justice on Job Satisfaction, it can be concluded as follows: 1) Distributive Justice has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction for FMCG Food Employees Environment. 2) Procedural Justice has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction for FMCG Food Employee Environment. 3) Interactional Justice has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction for FMCG Food Employee Environment. 4) Organizational

Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction for Food FMCG Employee Environment. 5) Distributive Justice has a negative and insignificant effect on Organizational Commitment to the Environment for Food FMCG Employees. 6) Procedural Justice has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment to FMCG Food Employee Environment. 7) Interactional Justice has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment to the Environment for Food FMCG Employees. 8) Organizational Commitment is positively and significantly capable of intervening in the relationship of Distributive Justice on Job Satisfaction for FMCG Food Employee Environment. 9) Organizational Commitment is positively and significantly capable of intervening in the relationship of Procedural Justice on Job Satisfaction for FMCG Food Employee Environment. 10) Organizational Commitment is positively and significantly able to intervene in the Interactive Justice relationship on Job Satisfaction for FMCG Food Employee environment.

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